

Virtual Antenna Array Based Channel Sounding at 300 GHz: Implementation and Field Measurements

Yejian Lyu, Fengchun Zhang, Zhiqiang Yuan, Pekka Kyösti, and Wei Fan

Abstract—Knowledge of spatial profiles of propagation channels holds significant importance in channel modeling, particularly in the sub-terahertz (sub-THz) frequency band spanning from 100 to 300 GHz. The directional scanning scheme (DSS) offers a straightforward and cost-effective means to achieve such purpose. However, the resulting spatial profiles are subject to the directional characteristics of the employed antenna (e.g., half-power beamwidth and sidelobes). The virtual antenna array (VAA) method, i.e., mechanically relocating a single antenna to specific spatial locations to construct a virtual antenna array, can achieve significant enhancement of the spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) through array signal processing. However, VAA requires phase-coherent measurements among virtual array elements, presenting a challenge to the channel-sounding implementation at sub-THz bands due to the highly sensitive phase at 1 mm level of the wavelength. In our previous work, we introduced a phase-coherent channel sounder capable of stabilizing the phase of the channel-sounding system. Leveraging this technology, we implement and validate the first 300 GHz VAA using an extremely large antenna array (ELAA) setup comprising 1200 array elements in the field measurements in this work. The measured results demonstrated the effectiveness of the VAA scheme, by offering significantly improved SNR and spatial resolution compared to the traditional DSS scheme.

Index Terms—Radio channel sounding, sub-terahertz, virtual antenna array (VAA), radio propagation

I. INTRODUCTION

With the escalating demand for higher data rates in wireless communication for more 6G applications [1], [2], the investigation into the untapped sub-terahertz (sub-THz) frequencies (i.e., 100-300 GHz) has emerged as a recent focal point of research. While sub-THz frequency bands offer the potential for enhanced data rates, numerous challenges arise within these bands, such as high signal attenuation, susceptibility to blockage, and distinct propagation characteristics compared to lower frequency spectra. Addressing these challenges necessitates the development of accurate and reliable radio channel models, which necessitate high-fidelity channel sounders tailored to sub-THz bands.

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Two main methods are used to record the sub-THz channel spatial profiles, namely directional scanning scheme (DSS) and virtual antenna array (VAA). In the literature, DSS stands out as the dominant method in sub-THz bands [3]–[7]. This method involves positioning directional antenna(s) at the center of the turntable(s), located within the transmitter (Tx) and/or receiver (Rx), and channel impulse response (CIR) is captured for each rotational angle by mechanically rotating the antenna(s). However, the angular resolution of the measured spatial profiles is constrained by the directivity of the employed antenna(s), potentially affecting the accuracy of parameter estimation and channel characterization.

The virtual antenna array (VAA) scheme [8]–[12] is an alternative approach due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness. This method involves systematically relocating a single antenna to various spatial positions, termed VAA elements, where the channel frequency response (CFR) or CIR is sequentially recorded. By employing suitable array signal processing algorithms, such as beamforming or maximum likelihood estimation algorithms, VAAs can achieve superior spatial resolution and significantly enhanced signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) compared to the DSS. However, VAA implementation requires coherent phase measurement across all VAA elements. Yet, achieving such phase coherence proves mechanically and RF electronically challenging in sub-THz bands due to observed phase instability issues [13].

The phase compensation scheme, which utilizes a feedback link to record the random phase change in the optical cable in the forward link (introduced by thermal or mechanical change) and then to compensate for the phase change in post-processing, has been implemented and validated up to 75–110 GHz in the state-of-the-art [8], [12]. In our previous work [14], we proposed phase-compensated channel sounders for 220–330 GHz, and back-to-back measurement was proposed. Though its application for future phase-coherent applications, e.g. the VAA scheme was highlighted, validation of the 300 GHz VAA in the field measurements remains absent in the literature to date. It is important to know to which extent the proposed 300 GHz phased compensation scheme works in practice. Practically speaking, we also need to select a suitable directional antenna in the VAA scheme, and therefore it is important to understand whether antenna directivity has an impact on the VAA scheme performance.

To fill these gaps, this paper presents the first 300 GHz VAA implementation, and field measurements. The validation measurements are performed in a clean entrance room scenario at 295–305 GHz. The VAA configuration is a virtual uniform circular array (UCA) with 1200 array elements, which can

be considered as an extremely large antenna array (ELAA). Note that this VAA concept can work for arbitrary array configurations. A modified classical beamforming (BF) algorithm is applied to acquire extremely high angular resolution. The measured narrowband power-angle-spectra (PASs) at 300 GHz from the DSS and VAA schemes are first compared to demonstrate the high angular resolution achieved by the VAA scheme. The wideband power-angle-delay profiles (PADPs) for the DSS and VAA schemes are illustrated and analyzed. Finally, the multipath components (MPCs) extracted from the PADPs are then compared with the room geometry, the observation is that the parameters of the MPCs (i.e., delay and angle-of-arrival (AoA)) are consistent with the room geometry.

II. STABILITY INVESTIGATION AND FIELD VALIDATION MEASUREMENTS

A. Stability investigation for VAA

In sub-THz bands (i.e., 100 GHz to 300 GHz), the wavelength reaches 1-3 mm, and the phase of the channel sounding system is highly sensitive to the mechanical movement of the turntable or positioner during the VAA measurements. Thus, we investigate the stability of the channel sounding system, employing two schemes:

- 1) **Electrical solution:** In our former study [12], [14], the radio-over-fiber (RoF)-enabled vector network analyzer (VNA)-based channel sounder, which is suitable for long-range channel measurements due to the lower signal loss in the optical fiber, is highly sensitive to the phase change due to the temperature change and mechanical stress. Thus, a phase-compensation scheme is employed to address this issue. For this sounder, the phase accuracy of the sub-THz channel sounding system was experimentally demonstrated to be within $\pm 7.5^\circ$ and $\pm 18.5^\circ$ in the frequency range of 220-288 GHz and 288-330 GHz, respectively. The high phase deviation for the higher band was mainly introduced by the frequency extender.
- 2) **Mechanical solution:** This paper also investigates the phase fluctuation caused by the movement of the turntable. A simple field measurement in a chamber has been conducted at 300 GHz with the phase sweeping within 8 s after one turntable movement. Note that we normalized the system and channel response, thus, we can directly obtain the phase fluctuation results. From the results, it can be observed that the phase fluctuates over 120° and the phase becomes stable only after 3.2 s, as shown in Fig. 1. Thus, according to this investigation, we set a waiting time of 3.5 s after turntable movement for the VAA measurements.

B. Measurement description

In the field measurements, the frequency range is set to 295-305 GHz with the number of frequency points of 5001. The intermediate frequency bandwidth (IFBW) (which influence the noise floor) is set to 500 Hz to ensure good dynamic range. The maximum detectable delay and path length are 500 ns and

Fig. 1: The phase fluctuation results.

Fig. 2: The diagram and photo of the measurement scenario. (a) Diagram of the scenario and Tx and Rx deployment; (b) Photo of the scenario.

150 m, respectively. The simplified diagram and photos of the measurement scenario are depicted in Fig. 2. The measurement scenario is an entrance hall with the size of $8.20 \times 4.78.8 \text{ m}^3$. The transmitter (Tx)-receiver (Rx) distance is 6.50 m. The Tx and Rx are placed in the same height of 1.25 m. The Tx is fixed, while the Rx is mounted on a turntable to form a virtual UCA with a radius r of 9.50 cm and a rotation step of 0.3° , corresponding to 1200 antenna array elements. According to the Fraunhofer distance equation, i.e., $d_{\text{far}} = \frac{2(D)^2}{\lambda}$, where $D = 2r$ is the aperture of the array and λ represents the wavelength, the distance for the far-field case of this VAA d_{far} is 72.2 m. The distance between the adjacent array elements is 0.497 mm, which is close to the half-wavelength of the highest measured frequency 305 GHz, i.e., 0.491 mm. The antenna used on the Tx side is a standard gain horn antenna with a wide azimuth half-power beamwidth (HPBW) of 36° and 15 dBi antenna gain (typical value and typed 261J-15/387).

Fig. 3: Comparison of the measured PAS and beamformed PAS at 300 GHz (narrowband) in both cases. (a) Wide-HPBW case; (b) Narrow-HPBW case.

In the measurement campaign, two types of standard gain horn antenna are employed to form the virtual UCA, i.e., wide-HPBW case and narrow-HPBW case. In the wide-HPBW case, we use the same antenna as the Tx side to be the array element, while in the narrow-HPBW case, the typical antenna gain and azimuth HPBW of the used antenna are 25.5 dBi and 8° (typed LB-3-25-A), respectively. The measurement time for a virtual UCA is approximately 8 hours. The VAA setup and measurement configurations are outlined in Table I.

TABLE I: VAA and scenario configurations.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Frequency	295-305 GHz	Frequency bandwidth	10 GHz
Number of points	5001	IFBW	500 Hz
Transmitted power	10 dBm	Tx & Rx height	1.25 m
VAA Radius	9.5 cm	Rotation step	0.3°
Number of elements	1200	Tx-Rx distance	6.50 m
Typ. Tx antenna gain	15 dBi	Typ. Tx HPBW	36°
Wide-HPBW case			
Typ. Rx antenna gain	15 dBi	Typ. Rx HPBW	36°
Narrow-HPBW case			
Typ. Rx antenna gain	25.5 dBi	Typ. Rx HPBW	8°

III. FIELD VALIDATION RESULTS

From the VAA measurements, we can directly acquire the channel frequency response (CFR) for each VAA element,

and the measured channel impulse responses (CIRs) can be obtained by applying the inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT). Note that in this paper, the Hanning window is used on the CFR to mitigate spectral leakage. In this paper, the CFRs are further processed by the modified classical BF [15] to obtain spatial channel profiles with a higher angular resolution for directive antenna-based VAA. The principle is that a window function is applied to select the effective antenna array elements to form a synthesized beam. The window sizes for the wide-HPBW and narrow-HPBW cases are 200-element and 120-element, corresponding to 60° and 36°, respectively. Note that the antenna gain has been normalized in the measured results and the antenna pattern is de-embedded in the BF results.

Fig. 3 depicts the comparison between the measured and beamformed PASs at the single-frequency (i.e., 300 GHz) in both wide-HPBW and narrow-HPBW cases. Note that the measured PAS is the power measured per orientation angle of the measurement antenna, which is obtained directly by taking the measured CFR at the single frequency (i.e., 300 GHz), while the beamformed PAS is obtained by applying the aforementioned beamforming algorithm to the measured PAS. The measured PAS in the wide-HPBW case has a low angular resolution, i.e., with a measured HPBW of 33° at 300 GHz, while the measured PAS in the narrow-HPBW case has a slightly higher angular resolution (a measured HPBW of 7.2°) at 300 GHz, as expected. Besides, due to the low antenna gain of the employed antenna in the wide-HPBW case, the dynamic range is too limited to detect multipath components. After performing the modified BF algorithm, the beam achieved by the VAA scheme can be synthesized and a higher angular resolution can be obtained. The HPBWs of the synthesized beam in the wide-HPBW and narrow-HPBW cases are 0.6° and 1.5°, respectively. Furthermore, with the help of the BF array gain, the dynamic range can be further improved. Comparing the measured and beamformed results, only one dominant path can be observed in the measured PAS, while three MPCs can be detected after BF, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the VAA scheme. The VAA scheme is highly effective both for the wide HPBW antenna and narrow HPBW cases. Both beamformed patterns offer excellent spatial resolution and much improved dynamic range. The wide-HPBW case offers slightly better spatial resolution results, possibly since more effective VAA elements are selected, which is an optimal balance between the array gain and angular resolution compared to the omnidirectional antenna-based VAA and narrow-HPBW case.

Fig. 4 illustrates the comparison between the PADPs for the DSS and VAA schemes in the wide-HPBW case. The comparison between the PADPs for the DSS and VAA schemes in the narrow-HPBW case is shown in Fig. 5. Note that 35 dB dynamic range is used in all of the PADPs to clearly illustrate the multipath components. With the help of the wide bandwidth (i.e., 10 GHz), the MPCs can be distinguished in the delay domain. The comparison of the PADPs demonstrates that the high angular resolution can be achieved by the phase-coherent VAA. Besides, the measured 300 GHz channels in this scenario are seen to be sparse and specular. In the wide-

Fig. 4: PADPs for the DSS and VAA schemes in the wide-HPBW case. (a) DSS scheme; (b) VAA scheme.

HPBW case, 6 MPCs are detected. The measured line-of-sight (LoS) path has the power, the delay, and the angle of -97.17 dB, 21.6 ns, and 0° , respectively. The measured delay corresponds to the distance of 6.48 m, which is close to the Tx-Rx distance in the measurements, while the measured LoS power is close to the free space path loss (FSPL) (i.e., 98.22 dB). Paths 2-5 are observed to be the reflections from different walls. After the BF algorithm, the power of the LoS path is observed to be -98.24 dB, which is also close to the measured LoS power and the FSPL, and the delay and angle of the LoS path are seen to be the same as those of the measured LoS. Paths 2-6 for the VAA scheme are observed to be close to those in the PADP for the DSS scheme.

In the narrow-HPBW case, we can observe 5 MPCs. The power of the measured LoS is found to be -98.43 dB. The LoS delay and angle are 21.6 ns and 0° , respectively. After BF, the LoS power, delay, and angle are -100.06 dB, 21.6 ns, and 0° , respectively. The parameters (i.e., power, delay, and angle) of paths 2-5 are observed to be close to those in the wide-HPBW case. Note that path 6 in the wide-HPBW case is the ground reflection due to the wide HPBW of the array element in the elevation (i.e., 29.71°) compared to only 6° HPBW in the elevation plane of the antenna in the narrow-HPBW case. Note that the height of the ceiling is 3.8 m, which means that the elevation angle of the reflection from the ceiling is 38° based on the geometry, thus, it is hard to observe the reflection of the ceiling in the results. Based on the estimated multipath parameters and the room geometry, we can plot the path trajectory, as shown in Fig. 6, which is in good agreement with the room geometry. Note that due to the narrow azimuth

Fig. 5: PADPs for the DSS and VAA schemes in the narrow-HPBW case. (a) DSS scheme; (b) VAA scheme.

Fig. 6: The relationship between the MPC parameters and the entrance geometry.

HPBW of the Tx antenna, we did not observe any reflection from the elevator.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented the first field measurements using the VAA scheme at 300 GHz in a clean entrance room scenario at 295 - 305 GHz. The VAA was designed to be a virtual UCA with a radius of 9.5 cm, and 1200 array elements. The PAS and PADP with DSS and VAA schemes were presented and compared for two types of directional antennas with different HPBW. The measured results demonstrated that with the help of the phase-compensated channel sounder and the turntable stability investigation in this work, sub-THz channels can be practically measured with very high angular and delay resolutions using the described VAA setup.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Yifa Li, Mengting Li, Qiyu Zeng, and Kim Olesen for their help with the measurements. The work was partially supported by the 21NRM03 MEWS project, which has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, and by the Participating States. The work was also supported by the HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-03 6G-SHINE project (Grant Agreement No. 101095738).

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